

Modern methods used in the determination of antioxidant activity

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Plants are the most important source of compounds that are very beneficial for the human body, including natural antioxidants. Therefore, the study of important compounds in the composition of useful plants and their use in human nutrition is one of the most important issues of our time. Antioxidants are substances that reduce oxidative stress by neutralizing the harmful effects of free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the body. They play an important role in human health, and are important in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, cancer, and aging processes. Therefore, the determination of antioxidant activity in plants, foods, and pharmaceuticals is one of the important areas in science and industry.

The normal natural metabolism of aerobic cells is accompanied by the formation of some oxygen free radicals. These free radicals, known as reactive oxygen species (ROS), include superoxide anion (O²⁻), peroxy (ROO[•]), alkoxy (RO[•]), hydroxyl (OH[•]), and nitrogen oxides. Of these radicals, hydroxyl and alkoxy are more reactive. Tocopherol, ascorbic acid, carotenoids and flavonoids found in plants are natural antioxidants belonging to phenolic compounds. Modern methods used to determine antioxidant activity are diverse and the method chosen depends on the purpose of the study.

Material and methods. DPPH, ABTS, FRAP are suitable for simple and rapid assessment; HPLC-MS/MS, electrochemical methods are suitable for precise analysis; cell-based and in vivo tests are more suitable for biological effect assessment. For the most reliable results, a combination of several methods is recommended.

Conclusion. In the research work, modern methods used in the study of antioxidant activity were investigated. As a result of the research, a number of modern methods were identified, and the results were presented in the form of tables and graphs. The method we used most often in our studies and also in other modern studies was DPPH.

Keywords: antioxidant, DPPH, FRAP, health, methods, radical